

Review Paper on Material by Partial Replacement of Fine Aggregate with Stone Dust in Interlocking Paver Block

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How to cite this paper: Ankit Dubey | Manawer Ali "Review Paper on Material by Partial Replacement of Fine Aggregate with Stone Dust in Interlocking Paver Block" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-5, August 2019, pp.2628-2630, <https://doi.org/10.31142/ijtsrd29218>

IJTSRD29218

pp.2628-2630,

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INTRODUCTION

Concrete is commonly used construction material due to its ease of availability, mouldability, rigidity and durability. It generally consists of binding material, fine aggregate, coarse aggregate and required quantity of water, where sand is normally used as fine aggregate. Due to rapid growth of construction activity, the available sources of natural sand are getting exhausted. Hence conservation of natural resources is great challenge for civil engineers since construction activities cannot be diminished as it is intimate able. The only way is to search an alternatives material which can fully or partially replaced naturally available material in construction. Stone dust is such an alternative material which can be effectively being used in construction as partial replacement of natural sand. This is a waste product obtained from aggregate crushing plant. Stone dust is well appropriate in terms of strength and economy over normal sand for medium grade concrete.

Rural Road property may be a key element of rural development, since it promotes access to economic and social services, thereby generating magnified agricultural productivity, non-agriculture employment likewise as non-agricultural productivity, that successively expands rural growth opportunities and real financial gain through that financial conditions are often reduced. A study disbursed by the International Food Policy analysis Institute on linkages between government expenditure associated financial condition in rural Asian country has unconcealed that an investment of Rs one large integer in roads lifts 1650 poor persons on top of the personal income.

Public investment on roads impacts rural financial condition through its impact on improved agricultural productivity, higher non-farm employment opportunities and magnified rural wages. Improvement in agricultural productivity not solely reduces rural financial condition directly by increasing financial gain of poor households, it additionally causes decline in financial condition indirectly by raising agricultural wages and lowering food costs (since poor households square measure web consumers of food grains). Similarly, magnified non-farm employment and better rural wages additionally enhance incomes of the agricultural poor and consequently, scale back rural financial condition.

Literature Survey

➤ **Jyothi D N 2018**, The present study is aimed at utilizing Waste marble powder and quarry sand as partial replacement of cement and fine aggregate in concrete and comparing it with conventional concrete. This experimental investigation is carried out in three phases in 1st phase M20 grade of concrete is produced by replacing cement with 0%, 5%, 10% & 15% of Marble Powder. In 2nd phase concrete is produced by replacing sand with 0%, 30%, 40% & 50% of quarry sand and in 3rd phase concrete is produced by replacing cement and fine aggregate in the percentage of 0%, 5%, 10% & 15% of Marble Powder and 0%, 30%, 40% & 50% of quarry dust respectively. It is found that the studies of concrete made of waste marble powder and quarry sand

increases at 10% and 40% respectively. Therefore the quarry dust and waste marble powder should be used in construction works, then the cost of construction would be saved significantly and the natural resources would be used efficiently.

- **Aghimien, Emmanuel Imuetinyan 2018**. The study revealed that the use of solid concrete for walkway construction is gradually fading away as most of the walkways newly constructed are done with the use of interlocking stones. This is as a result of the need for beautification and the need to meet up with present trend. The major defects associated with solid concrete walkways within the institution are cracks and breakages while that of interlocking stones are presence of vegetative growth in between voids, removal of interlocking stones and undulating walkways
- **Atul Thakur et al (2017)** studied partial replacement (by weight) of cement with RHA in paver blocks for determining the change in the compressive strength, water absorption and abrasive resistance of paver blocks. Partial replacement of cement in different percentage as like 0%, 15%, 20%, 25%, 30%, 35% and 45% has been done. The compressive strength has been determined at the end of 7, 28 and 56 days, water absorption test and abrasion resistance have been determined at 28 days.

- **Vikas Kumar Patel (2017)** The rapid development of housing and infrastructure from last one decade continuously takes place in India. Along with that naturally, the product required to overcome this development produce in mass quantities like Pavement blocks, which are known as industrial products of precast made up by concrete, having various shapes and sizes utilizes in huge quantity in housing and infrastructure construction. The conventional materials to manufacturing these blocks utilize in large quantity, which may create an impact on natural recourses. To overcome this impact we can use different materials such as, Sisal fiber, waste glass, fly ash etc. which helps to save natural recourses and achieve economy so that buyers and sellers of this type of materials can also get benefited. The present experimental research investigation examines the effect of fly ash at the partial replacement of cement. Experiment is done on M33, M43 and M53 mix, with 5%, 10%, 15%, 20% & 25% partial replacement of cement. After getting an optimum percentage of all these, further experimental work is intended for the use of all these three in a single paving block. The replaced ingredients in this research are fly ash. Experimentation is carried out to find the workability test, water absorption test, compressive strength and flexural strength of the concrete paving blocks. Further, these studies compare an economical aspect of the conventional product and newly manufactured product.
- **Atul Thakur et al (2017)** studied partial replacement (by weight) of cement with RHA in paver blocks for determining the change in the compressive strength, water absorption and abrasive resistance of paver blocks. Partial replacement of cement in different percentage as like 0%, 15%, 20%, 25%, 30%, 35% and 45% has been done. The compressive strength has been determined at the end of 7, 28 and 56 days, water absorption test and abrasion resistance have been determined at 28 days.
- **B. Kaviya (2016)** studied for manufacturing paving blocks with crusher dust is studied. Paving blocks replaced with crusher dust by various percentages and its properties have also been studied. The results show that replacing sand with crusher dust has a minimal reduction in weight and also it leads to the economy. Since the availability of sand is reducing now-a-days using of crusher dust will reduce polluting the environment since it is being dumped in many places.
- **Hanumantharao Chappidi 2016** The concept of replacement of natural fine aggregate by quarry dust which is highlighted in the study could boost the consumption of quarry dust generated from quarries. By replacement of quarry dust, the requirement of land fill area can be reduced and can also solve the problem of natural sand scarcity. The availability of sand at low cost as a fine aggregate in concrete is not suitable and that is the reason to search for an alternative material.
- **Ahmed Omran, Arezki Tagnit-Hamou, 15 April 2016,** Examined that the blended shaded glass can't be reused and is regularly discarded in landfills, causing evident natural issues. So if this glass subsequent to pounding to same fineness as bond permit its utilization as supplementary cementitious materials specially it has

pozzolanic conduct. The examination gave an account of in this shows the in situ execution of cement containing Glass Powder utilized as an incomplete substitution of concrete at different development locales including inside and outside chunks and auxiliary divider components. Notwithstanding the natural advantages the solid made with 20% Glass Powder substitution indicated increments in 91-days compressive quality (7%). 28-days rigidity (35%) and 28-days flexure quality (4%) contrasted with reference blends without Glass Powder. A huge increment in protection from chloride-particle entrance can be gotten when utilizing Glass Powder concrete.

Problem identification

- Natural resources are decreasing in all over the world and increasing wastes from industries generated simultaneously.

Objectives

The objectives of the research are outlined below:

- The objective of the research is to study the effect of the use of Stone dust as a replacement of fine aggregate for Paver Blocks.

CONCLUSION

The compressive strength of concrete paver block by replacing the 40% sand by stone dust the strength increases stone dust as at 7, 14 and 28 days respectively in M-30 concrete. As compared to the conventional concrete.

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